

Data Readiness

Applied to EOSCLIMA Use Cases

Summary	Working Paper in Data Readiness
Audience	RDMI Community
Status	Draft

Date	Authors	Description	Version
26-02-2020	W Hugo, A Linke	Presented to Forum of Insurers (not included here)	0.1
08-11-2023	W Hugo	Basic Readiness Framework	0.2
07-12-2023	W Hugo, C Hof	Alignment with 01-01 Proposal - use cases	0.3
11-12-2023	W Hugo	Alignment with EOSCLIMA Use Cases	0.4
13-12-2023	W Hugo	Added HE project outputs	0.5
11-01-2024	W Hugo	Further elaboration and glossary	0.6
16-01-2024	W Hugo	Added examples and created questionnaire	0.7
23-01-2024	EOSCLIMA Consortium	Review and Additions	0.8
10-04-2-25	W Hugo	Publication	1.0

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Reviewers	EOSCLIMA Consortium Members

An Example: Climate Risk and Vulnerability

Analysis-ready data: Climate models predict future average and maximum temperatures for a number of scenarios. The variables, spatial and temporal scale and accuracy of the data, and its other dimensions are defined based on community-adopted standards and consensus, and are made available with standardised schema, syntax, and semantics.

Decision-ready data: Climate model outputs are mapped to the ‘perils’ or ‘hazards’ for a climate risk and vulnerability framework. This requires a standardised definition of such hazards (say ‘heat waves’), and transformation of the climate model data into predictions of the frequency/probability, coverage, and intensity of heat waves. In technical terms, we are mapping the semantics of analysis-ready data to the semantics of decision frameworks, and in some cases the mapping is not trivial and/ or requires computation. There can be many other decision-ready datasets based on the same analysis-ready dataset - for example, together with precipitation and humidity forecasts, the temperature forecast is also used to predict hydrological, agricultural, ecological, and meteorological drought.

Benefit (Assessment) Framework: Decision-ready data in itself mostly does not directly translate into improved decision-making and policy - the benefit that we want to realise for society.. If we know the future frequency, cover, and intensity of heat waves, we do not yet have any idea of what our policy response should be. To advise on this, we need to combine multiple decision-ready datasets: the distribution of the population now and in future, with its estimated age and income distribution (older people are more susceptible, and the poor are less resilient in dealing with the issue), likely nature of housing and shelter, current and future availability of water supply, emergency medical services, and so on. The scope of decision-ready data (evidence) needed to support a policy decision can be defined as a ‘benefit framework’ and is needed to link decision-ready data to its role in a benefit framework.

How does open science translate into societal benefit? By supporting decision and policy formulation based on evidence. But - to achieve such a benefit, we need technical as well as procedural and governance arrangements to be in place. [More ...](#)

Example: Stepwise improvement of a resource

Data Readiness Framework

Data Readiness Level	<p>The data readiness level scale or assignment is designed to summarise the potential use or re-use of a dataset (resource), based on its characteristics. It is a semi-qualitative process to assess alignment, achieved by determining whether a set of desirable features or characteristics are present in the metadata and the data for a dataset. <i>A similar approach may be possible for other research outputs, but is out of scope here.</i></p>
Resource Creation	<p>Resources are mostly created within environments controlled by researchers, such as personal, institutional, project, instrument, or cloud-based storage for data that is being created, quality assured, processed, and otherwise prepared for publication. These instances of a data object are generally not of any concern to outside parties, although there is sometimes utility in sharing with collaborators in the field.</p>
P Publication-Ready	<p>Data that is publication-ready generally meet two requirements: the data has been quality-assured to a standard or level of confidence expected by the end user community, and the metadata for the data object meets minimum requirements to make it <i>citable</i>, <i>findable</i>, and minimally <i>re-usable</i>. This minimum metadata expectation varies between schema (which, in turn, are sometimes domain and or format-specific) but broadly cover about 15-20 common metadata elements.</p>
R Reproducibility-Ready	<p>Reproducible data exhibits are a number of additional characteristics, mostly related to metadata and links to other instances of research outputs or concepts: aspects such as methodology, research protocols, instrumentation, code, processing platforms, and the like are described in enough detail for a third party to attempt reproduction of the research output.</p>
A Analysis-Ready	<p>Analysis-ready data is generally offered in such a way that it supports <i>technical (schematic and syntactic) and semantic interoperability within a specific scientific domain</i>. It more often than not requires extension of minimum metadata with format- and/ or domain-specific metadata. In practice, this usually involves defining the exact semantic meaning of the variables, measuring instruments, units of measure, confidence intervals, precision, etc. of the data, and making the data available through standard API interfaces supporting the formats (schema) agreed by the community. Data from different providers can be collated without major rework. Directly supports intra-disciplinary <i>interoperability</i> and <i>reusability</i>.</p>
D Decision-Ready	<p>Decision-ready data maps the semantics of an analysis ready dataset to the semantics of a societal question or challenge. At times, this involves additional computation and/ or the combination of multiple input datasets to support the computation, and it often involves application of assumptions about future scenarios, optimisation, and risk mitigation, for example. Supports <i>cross or inter-disciplinary interoperability</i> and <i>reusability</i>.</p>
A AI-Ready	<p>AI-readiness presents a relatively new and specialised case of analysis-ready or decision-ready data, where the semantic and schematic aspects of the data is presented in such a way that it can easily be reasoned over by AI or ML routines, and where it is simpler to link the content of the datasets into a training dataset on the basis of semantics. The context of the data (e.g. its reproducibility attributes) is important for training models. AI-focused metadata (e.g. Croissant) is available</p>

Nature of Data and Metadata	Identifier Metadata	Kernel Metadata	Custom Metadata	Semantic Enhancements	Annotations
<p>Description</p>	<p>Identifier metadata is metadata that is maintained by the (usually centralised) registry of persistent identifiers.</p> <p>There are many PID stacks that can be used, but as an example, DOIs issued by DataCite and Crossref, and ePIC handles, are all based on the Handle System. For Handles, the identifier metadata is quite rudimentary and largely contains information on when it was created and by whom, but it does not store any other metadata directly.</p>	<p>Kernel metadata is usually standardised, and most often does not reflect any domain or format-specific customisation.</p> <p>DataCite DOIs, for example, store kernel metadata based on a schema agreed by the community, and there is a very limited subset of the schema that is mandatory to be able to obtain a DOI. As such, it is not very useful for findability or re-use, and largely serves as a stable citation.</p> <p>Kernel metadata is not considered to be authoritative.</p>	<p>Custom metadata is routinely provided by the originator of a research output, and maintained and optionally improved by a curator at a suitable repository. Such metadata more often than not extends or replaces kernel metadata with domain- and/ or format specific schema. It is much more suitable for findability and re-use than kernel metadata.</p> <p>Some metadata schema allow description of the semantics of the data object, but some do not, and such detail is often missing.</p> <p>Custom metadata is considered to be the authoritative copy and is usually the target of PID resolution.</p>	<p>One can enhance metadata and data by formalising semantics. For data in the natural, physical, and engineering sciences, this often entails describing the variable, its dimensions (space and time coverage, taxonomy, etc.), methodology, instruments, and units of measure at the hand of community-agreed vocabularies or definitions.</p> <p>In a broader sense, the context of the object (project and research context, version history, reproducibility context) can also be described using standardised approaches and vocabulary.</p> <p>Traditional metadata schema often do not cover these aspect adequately, or details are maintained externally.</p>	<p>In cases where the additional metadata or data that one would like to associate or combine with a research output is maintained elsewhere (for example the definition of a variable), or if it is an attribute of a relationship between two distinct research outputs (for example a dataset linked to code or a publication) annotations are the best mechanism for recording and maintaining such links. Increasingly, data of this kind is maintained in Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs).</p> <p>We also have informal annotation possibilities that can inform in terms of fitness for use, data quality, and other types of community feedback - for example using hypothes.is</p>

Data Readiness Level	Identifier Metadata	Kernel Metadata	Custom Metadata	Semantic Enhancements	Annotations
Resource Creation	In the EOSCLIMA project, each use case will maintain its own conventions in this regard.			Not applicable	Out of Scope Strong Recommendation Recommendation
Publication-Ready	Registration of a persistent identifier. This is achieved indirectly by registering kernel metadata.	Minimum (mandatory) kernel metadata is available. Agree on provider(s).	Domain and/ or format-specific metadata is provided. Agree on schemata and quality/ completeness.	Not applicable	
Reproducibility-Ready	Not applicable	Register relation to a LinkSet in kernel metadata using Signposting if possible, else as a named relation	Implement Signposting with one relation to a Linkset, RO-Crate provided in Linkset	RO-Crate Context: Instrument(s) definition Methodology definition Code definition	Not Applicable
Analysis-Ready	Not applicable	Optionally, the Linkset can reference an RDF or json-LD based Data Dictionary, and provide query endpoints for mappings to analysis tools	Data description based on domain-specific essential or standard variables included into metadata	Linkset Context: Variables, Instrument(s), Methodology, units of measure, dimensions defined in metadata and data using vocabularies	Semantic Mappings to Analysis Tools - matching datasets with generic third-party services and applications
Decision-Ready	Not applicable	Optionally, the Linkset can reference query endpoints for mappings to decision tools and workflows	Societal challenge keywords mapped from formal vocabularies for that purpose	Linkset Context: Providing explicit mappings between dataset variables and the role it would fill in some decision framework	Semantic Mappings to Decision Tools and Workflows - matching datasets to specific third-party services
AI-Ready	Not applicable	Not applicable	Croissant Metadata Available as json-LD	Data converted to json-LD	Semantic links as json-LD